

Ground Fault Detection Method for Variable Speed Drives

José Manuel Guerrero , *Senior Member, IEEE*

Abstract—The use of variable speed drives made essential the presence of power electronic in electrical systems. The ac to dc and dc to ac conversions, thanks to rectifiers and inverters cause difficulties in the ground fault detection. In this article, a new method to detect ground faults in variable speed drives is presented. It is based on the analysis of the terminal voltage signal of a grounding resistor connected between the neutral at the secondary of the main power transformer and ground. Attending to the waveform, the ground fault can be detected on the ac grid side, dc positive or negative terminals, or ac inverter side. To verify the method, numerous simulations and experimental tests in a 140-kW power converter were carried out achieving satisfactory results.

Index Terms—AC–AC power conversion, electrical fault detection, fault currents, fault diagnosis, power system faults.

NOMENCLATURE

A_k	Real component of the grounding voltage phasor.
B_k	Imaginary component of the grounding voltage phasor.
C	Capacitance.
f	Frequency.
f_1	AC grid fundamental frequency.
f_1'	AC controlled side fundamental frequency.
I_{2n}	Secondary rated current.
L	Inductance.
k	Number of harmonic.
N	Number of samples registered in a period.
n	Number of the evaluated sample.
R_f	Ground fault resistance.

José Manuel Guerrero is with the Energy and Fuels Department, ET-SIME, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, 28003 Madrid, Spain (e-mail: josemanuel.guerrero@upm.es).

Gustavo Navarro is with the Spanish Public Research Centre on Energy, Environment and Technology, CIEMAT, Ministerio de Innovación, Ciencia y Universidades, 28037 Madrid, Spain (e-mail: gustavo.navarro@ciemat.es).

Kumar Mahtani and Carlos A. Platero are with the Automatic, Electric and Electronic and Industrial Computer Engineering Department, ET-SII, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, 28006 Madrid, Spain (e-mail: kumar.mahtani@upm.es; carlosantonio.platero@upm.es).

R_g	Grounding resistor.
S_n	Rated power.
T_{DC}	Threshold for dc fault detection.
T_{AC}	Threshold for ac fault detection.
U_{gnd}	Grounding resistor voltage.
U_{1n}	Primary rated voltage.
U_{2n}	Secondary rated voltage.
u_{gnd}	Instant value of the grounding resistor voltage.
Z	Phase impedance.

I. INTRODUCTION

HIGH presence of power electronics in electrical systems is nowadays essential to control efficiently the electrical drives, wind power variable speed power generation, or HVdc transmission, among others. Then, the diagnosis and protection of this type of system is a crucial task, e.g., against ground faults [1].

The control of converters, rectifiers or inverters, makes possible the maximum power point tracking (MPPT) in photovoltaic and wind energy generation, allows the variable speed operation of generators or motors, as well as the increasing of the efficiency in renewable energies with reduction of the polluting emissions. For these purposes voltage converter control [2], current converter control [3], [4], or torque converter control [4] are used, among others.

One of the main problems in the insertion of converters is the lack of stability when a fault appears [5]. Converters have difficulties in maintaining the frequency on the ac grid side due to the lack of inertia, but with virtual inertias, the problem is softened [6]. In the case of faults in dc grids, the currents have a quick gradient development [7] that can originate several damages to the equipment.

However, the most common type of faults in an electrical system are ground faults. They occur when the insulation is deteriorated [8] to the extent of the disappearing of the insulation material due to overcurrents or high temperatures, aging, over-voltage, etc. [9]. What is more, if another ground fault happens, a leakage current will circulate through the ground to return between ground faults [10].

The objective of diagnosis and detection of ground faults in the electrical field is to locate, or, otherwise, to detect the first ground fault before a second one occurs [11]. In this topic, numerous studies have been done in photovoltaic power plants [12], HVdc lines [13], high resistance grounded ac grids [14], or controlled electrical drives [15], among others.

In the case of use power converters, the alternation between ac stages and dc stages implies as much presence of detectors and actuators as ac or dc stages exist [16].

Due to this problem, the authors proposed a new method to detect ground faults in [1]. Also, previous works were done by them for isolated electrical variable frequency drives fed from batteries by use of high-impedance grounding resistors in dc/ac systems [10]. As an extension of the research line, in this article, a new ground fault detection method is developed to differentiate different types of ground faults in any ac or dc side of variable speed drives, fed from isolated neutral grids. Critical process facilities are normally supplied by isolated or high-resistance grounded power systems, which limit the ground fault current to values below 10 A [17]. The method is based on the installation of a resistor connected between the neutral of the main power transformer and ground. Then, the analysis of the voltage or current in this grounding resistor allows the detection of ground faults. It is possible to identify if the fault is the ac grid side, dc link, or ac variable frequency side of the variable speed drive.

This article has the next structure: Section II analyzes the state of the previous art. Then, Section III presents the methodology of the newly proposed method. The computer simulations, that verify the operation of the ground fault detection method, are displayed and evaluated in Section IV. After some experimental tests have been done and their results are explained in Section V. Finally, Section VI concludes with the main contributions of the manuscript.

II. STATE OF THE ART

The detection and protection of the electrical system against ground faults are important tasks. In this field, numerous techniques have been developed for the different systems.

In ac power systems, some useful protection relays and detection devices are normally used as follows.

In differential current relays (ANSI 87), if a ground fault appears, a leakage current flows through the fault and returns to different grounding points of the grid. To detect it, the leakage current is measured at one or both terminals of the protected system [18]. Then, in case of two devices, if the currents are not similar neither have the same sign it produces the protections' trip [19]. Also, in case of one device, ground faults would be detected only downstream the protection. For neutral ungrounded systems, the detection by residual current measurement is not suitable. Moreover, the use of some residual current devices in power electronics presents certain problems such as unwanted trips in presence of harmonics [20], as well as for dc faults due to transformers' saturation.

Another well-known technique for ac systems is based on the measurement of the currents' zero sequence component in case of a ground fault (ANSI 51N) [21]. This component flows through the grounding impedance. With this procedure, it is not possible to detect faults close to the neutral. Regarding synchronous machines, only the first 95% of the stator is usually protected [22].

In order to protect the remaining part of the windings, there are other techniques. Some of them are based on the third harmonic

produced by the machine, which is measured at the generator's grounding resistor [23]. Therefore, ground faults in the neutral and in areas close to it can be detected [23], [24].

As said before, the detection of ground faults in nonsolid earthed systems is difficult, as in the case of overhead lines [25], [26]. To solve this problem, the under-impedances relays (ANSI 21) can also be used. The impedance is calculated from the measurement of the current and voltage of each phase [27]. If the measured impedance is lower than a certain threshold, the protection will trip [28]. Moreover, it can be estimated where the fault is and which is its arc resistance [29]. The problem with this type of protection is their limited application to ac transmission and distribution grids.

Furthermore, a number of protection relays and detection apparatus exist for dc power systems. In this field, the following methods can be highlighted:

First, a novel method to detect faults in dc linking bus systems is based on the discharge ratio of their capacitors [30]. If a fault appears, the capacitor starts to discharge faster than in a normal operation. Depending on how low or high the fault resistance is, the capacitor's discharge gradient will be higher or lower, respectively.

Another method contemplates the emplacement of emplacement of a grounded AC current source in an energized part of the dc system to ground [31], [32]. In this type of devices, the ac current is not registered unless a ground fault occurs. In that situation, the current returns from the ground to the ac source. Then, the current is measured with an ammeter at the ac source ground connection and an alarm signal is sent. This method is also valid if the frequency of the ac source's emitted signal is different from the fundamental current of an ac system [33].

Additionally, a method to be highlighted is the one where the fault current gradient is used to trip the protection [34]. Depending on the growth of the current gradient and the voltage change ratio's drop, the protection must trip. In this case, the detection and protection are guaranteed, but there can be a problem if this gradient is provoked by external circumstances such as works or operations on the transmission lines, external faults, or energizations. All of these previous methods can be used in systems with converters, but each side of a converter requires at least one of them. The high use of instrumentation can make the system's protection exceedingly expensive. Then, new methods to identify ground faults must be developed as presented in this article.

III. METHODOLOGY FOR THE GROUND FAULT DETECTION

In this section, the operating principles of the proposed ground fault detection method are presented. This method is motivated by the existence of power converters that transform the voltages and currents in the same circuitry from ac to dc and inversely. Then, faults in different parts of the system become difficult to detect.

For this reason, in this article, the placement of a ground fault detector in a strategic point of the circuitry is presented. The ground fault detector consists in the connection of a grounding resistor (R_g) between the neutral point of the low voltage side in

Fig. 1. Grounding resistor R_g in a common topology of variable speed drives with a frequency measuring device at motor terminals.

the main power transformer and ground, as shown in Fig. 1. In this figure, a common circuit typology of a variable speed drive is presented along with the ground fault detection device.

From left to right, a grounding resistor is placed at the secondary of the main power transformer that feeds the electrical system provided with power electronics. The power electronics comprise a rectifier with IGBTs that transform the grid ac voltage to dc voltage, a capacitor that keeps the voltage constant thanks to the converter's control and an inverter that produces the variable fundamental frequency (f_1') ac voltage to operate the electric motor at variable speed.

In this scenario, numerous ground faults can take place such as a fault on the ac grid side, on the dc positive pole, on the dc negative pole or on the ac inverter side. In all these cases, a leakage current will return from ground to the neutral of the main power transformer circulating through R_g but the waveforms will be different attending to the fault location.

In order to detect the fault, the voltage at the terminals of the grounding resistor is measured. Given the existence of a ground fault resistance (R_f), the terminal voltage measured in R_g is written as follows:

$$U_{\text{gnd}} = \frac{R_g}{R_g + R_f} \cdot U. \quad (1)$$

However, in case of no ground fault resistance, all the ground fault voltage will be registered in R_g . In the opposite situation, when the ground fault resistance takes a high value, the grounding resistor terminal voltage will be lower and the fault would be difficult to detect. Nevertheless, low terminal voltage registered in R_g gives an idea of the insulation condition if the leakage current starts growing slowly from 0.

An additional topic to remark in the detection process is the possibility of identifying where the fault was produced. It is achievable if a waveform analysis of the terminal voltage signal in R_g is carried out.

For an ac grid ground fault, a 50/60 Hz current (determined by the grid) will flow through R_g . It will have low content in harmonics because the power electronics will not affect in the fault current path.

If the ground fault occurs on the dc side, two possible locations are considered: at the positive terminal or at the negative one.

Fig. 2. Grounding resistor terminal voltage polarity for a ground fault at the positive terminal of the dc side.

Fig. 3. Grounding resistor terminal voltage polarity for a ground fault at the negative terminal of the dc side.

Then, a dc component in the registered voltage waveform will appear, and evaluating its sign, a dc positive or a dc negative ground fault is detected for negative or positive signs, respectively, as shown in Figs. 2 and 3.

Finally, for an ac inverter side ground fault a pulsed voltage waveform with the operation frequency of the electrical machine will be registered returning from ground to the neutral secondary transformer. The waveform also depends on the filters and stray capacitances between the phase and ground. Once the voltage waveform signal at the grounding resistor terminals is measured, a detection algorithm is executed, as seen in Fig. 4.

In this algorithm, a fast Fourier transformed (FFT) is done to detect the voltage phasors at fundamental frequencies of the

Fig. 4. Ground fault detector device algorithm.

ac grid side or the ac inverter side, f_1 and f_1' , respectively. In addition, the dc component must be calculated as the average value of the sampled period. The ac phasors are calculated in the next equations as

$$A_k = \frac{2}{N} \cdot \sum_{n=1}^N u_{\text{gnd}}(n) \cdot \cos\left(\frac{2 \cdot \pi \cdot k \cdot n}{N}\right) \quad (2)$$

$$B_k = \frac{2}{N} \cdot \sum_{n=1}^N u_{\text{gnd}}(n) \cdot \sin\left(\frac{2 \cdot \pi \cdot k \cdot n}{N}\right) \quad (3)$$

$$U_{\text{gnd}.k} = \sqrt{A_k^2 + B_k^2}. \quad (4)$$

Once the phasors are calculated, they are compared with a certain threshold previously adjusted. Three independent thresholds, $T.AC_g$, $T.DC$, and $T.AC_i$, can be set up for ac grid, dc, and ac inverter sides, respectively.

Another important fact is that the detection device can differentiate in which pole the ground fault has been produced by analyzing its polarity if the fault occurs on the dc side. As explained before, if the polarity of the dc component is negative, the ground fault is on the positive pole. Nevertheless, for positive polarity the faulty pole is the negative one.

Finally, once the ac side frequency and waveform's phasor (or in dc side case, its average value and polarity) are calculated, an alarm is emitted to external devices.

With this method, the problem of detecting ground faults in systems with high presence of power electronics is solved in an efficient and economical way. However, to verify it, simulations and experimental tests must be carried out.

IV. COMPUTER SIMULATIONS

With the aim of validating the proposed methodology, numerous simulations of ground faults in a variable speed drive comprising ac-dc and dc-ac converters have been performed on MATLAB Simulink. The simulations scenarios try to emulate the Fig. 1 as shown in Fig. 5 where the simulation setup is presented.

A. Computer Model

The simulation model includes the following stages:

Fig. 5. Ground faults simulation setup in a variable speed drive in MATLAB Simulink (1: ac grid side; 2: dc link bus; 3: ac inverter side).

1) *Three-Phase AC Load*: It has phase impedances, Z , of $50 + j\omega \cdot 2 \times 10^{-5} \Omega$. This impedance could be anyone as the fault current is not affected by the type of load due to a high R_{gnd} value. Also, in this side of the inverter, parasitic capacitances to ground of 0.25 pF, self-capacitances of 0.1 pF and L filters of 3 mH were considered.

2) *DC Bus Linking the Inverter With the Rectifier*: It is formed by two cable resistances for positive and negative poles of $0.5 + j\omega \cdot 6 \times 10^{-5} \Omega$ and their respective line to ground capacities of 0.25 pF for each conductor. Also, two switches have been placed in both poles of the dc bus to activate the inverter once the dc capacitor, which maintains the voltage at the dc bus, is charged up to 650 V. The capacitor's charge is done by the rectifying process from the grid. This capacitor, C , has a value of 1638 μF .

3) *AC Grid Circuit*: It is a 400 V/50 Hz low voltage power system. The considered circuit corresponds to the secondary side of the distribution transformer. It has been simulated as three ideal voltage sources with neutral accessible, where the grounding resistor is connected. The rectifier includes an ac phase inductances of 0.3 mH and some resistances of 0.1 Ω simulating ohmic losses. The grounding resistor considered has a value of 4.7 k Ω . In this way the ground fault is limited to a few milliamperes.

Once the circuit is built, the inverter control is established. The rectifier is configured as a voltage source of 650 V_{DC} for the capacitor's charge, and the inverter feeds the controlled ac side with a 25 Hz current waveform ($f_1' = 25$ Hz).

When the simulation configuration was completed, some faults were performed with ground fault resistances, R_f , of 0, 4.7 k Ω and 10 k Ω . These represent no impedance (maximum fault current), once and twice the grounding resistance, respectively.

They were located on phase "c" of the ac grid side, on the positive and negative poles of the dc link and on phase "c" of the ac controlled side.

B. Simulation Results

The simulations were carried out for a time interval of 100 ms. Afterward, some waveforms were registered for the aforementioned faults (0 Ω , 4.7 k Ω , and 10 k Ω). But first, a healthy operating conditions test has been performed, achieving negligible

Fig. 6. Grounding resistor terminal voltage waveform for healthy conditions.

Fig. 7. Grounding resistor terminal voltage waveforms for ground faults on the AC grid side. Ground fault resistances, $R_f = 0 \Omega$, $4.7 \text{ k}\Omega$, and $10 \text{ k}\Omega$.

voltage values as shown in Fig. 6. In healthy operation, no fault currents circulate through the grounding resistor, consequently, the voltage should also be null.

For ac grid side faults, sinusoidal voltage waveforms are recorded in the grounding resistor, as it can be seen in Fig. 7. In this figure, it can be appreciated that an increment in the ground fault resistance results in an amplitude reduction in the grounding resistor terminal voltage, U_{gnd} . For high ground fault resistances, low amplitudes are registered according to (1). Additionally, the high-frequency noises in the voltage waveform are provoked by parasitic capacitances on the ac controlled side and the dc-link side.

However, these noises are low because the fault current does not circulate through the power converter.

Another possibility is the occurrence of ground faults on the negative or positive pole of the dc bus. For these cases, the voltage waveform registered for faults on the negative pole with ground faults resistances of 0Ω , $4.7 \text{ k}\Omega$, and $10 \text{ k}\Omega$ are displayed in Figs. 8–10, respectively.

Also, faults on the positive pole with the same resistances are shown in Figs. 11–13, respectively.

For ground faults located on the dc side, it is proven that a dc component appears in the registered voltage signal.

This waveform has the opposite sign to the polarity where the fault takes place. Its value depends again on the ground fault resistance, R_f , as explained in (1). However, a pulsed component emerges caused by the rectifier control and IGBTs switching to maintain the voltage on the dc link.

Fig. 8. Grounding resistor terminal voltage waveform for a ground faults on the negative pole of the dc link with a fault resistance, $R_f = 0 \Omega$.

Fig. 9. Grounding resistor terminal voltage waveform for a ground fault on the negative pole of the dc link with $R_f = 4.7 \text{ k}\Omega$.

Fig. 10. Grounding resistor terminal voltage waveform for a ground fault on the negative pole of the dc link with $R_f = 10 \text{ k}\Omega$.

Fig. 11. Grounding resistor terminal voltage waveform for a ground fault on the positive pole of the dc link with $R_f = 0 \Omega$.

Fig. 12. Grounding resistor terminal voltage waveform for a ground fault on the positive pole of the dc link with $R_f = 4.7 \text{ k}\Omega$.

Fig. 13. Grounding resistor terminal voltage waveform for a ground fault on the positive pole of the dc link with $R_f = 10 \text{ k}\Omega$.

Fig. 14. Grounding resistor terminal voltage waveform registered for a ground fault on the ac inverter side. Ground fault resistance, $R_f = 0 \Omega$.

The detector device should identify the fault on the negative pole, distinguishing it from an ac ground fault for having a noticeable dc component in comparison with the fundamental component in the range of the ac grid side (f_1) or ac controlled side (f_1'). In case of positive pole faults, the amplitudes are similar to the previous cases, but the dc component sign is negative.

Finally, some ac inverter side ground faults have been performed. In this type of faults, the waveform registered also contains high-frequency components due to the modulated voltage. Thus, the noise in the registered voltage waveform for the ac inverter side is higher than on the ac grid side due to the IGBTs switching, parasitic capacitances and filters. It can be clearly seen in Figs. 14–16 for ground faults resistance of 0Ω , $4.7 \text{ k}\Omega$, and $10 \text{ k}\Omega$ respectively in comparison to Fig. 7.

Fig. 15. Grounding resistor terminal voltage waveform registered for a ground fault on the ac inverter side. Ground fault resistance, $R_f = 4.7 \text{ k}\Omega$.

Fig. 16. Grounding resistor terminal voltage waveform registered for a ground faults on the AC inverter side. Ground fault resistance, $R_f = 10 \text{ k}\Omega$.

Fig. 17. FFT for ac grid, negative pole, and ac inverter side faults with $R_f = 0 \Omega$.

With these simulations, the method is verified. The waveform's frequency defines the faulty ac side of the converter, or, if a dc side fault is detected, its polarity identifies the pole where the fault is taking place.

The most unfavorable scenario can appear when the frequency on the ac inverter side is the same as on the ac grid side, in which case, the switching frequency must be analyzed (5 kHz). This parameter can distinguish between a fault on the ac grid side if the waveform has no considerable noises, or a fault on the ac inverter side in the opposite case.

For instance, Fig. 17 shows the FFT for ground faults on the ac grid side, dc negative pole, and ac controlled side of the power converter for $R_f = 0 \Omega$. Here, the noise allows to distinguish between faults. In the case of a ground fault on the RL load side

TABLE I
GROUNDING RESISTOR VOLTAGE, FFT OBTAINED IN SIMULATIONS

Fault location Fault resistance (R_f)	$U_{gnd.DC}$ [V]	$U_{gnd.25Hz}$ [V]	$U_{gnd.50Hz}$ [V]	$U_{gnd.5kHz}$ [V]
AC Grid				
$R_f = 0$	0.023	7.55×10^{-3}	229.32	3.83×10^{-3}
$R_f = 4.7 \text{ k}\Omega$	0.012	3.89×10^{-3}	114.66	3.90×10^{-3}
$R_f = 10 \text{ k}\Omega$	0.007	2.38×10^{-3}	73.32	5.67×10^{-3}
Positive pole				
$R_f = 0$	-324.52	0.15	0.34	48.90
$R_f = 4.7 \text{ k}\Omega$	-162.26	8.53×10^{-2}	0.17	24.44
$R_f = 10 \text{ k}\Omega$	-103.77	8.59×10^{-2}	9.26×10^{-2}	15.62
Negative pole				
$R_f = 0$	+324.30	0.18	0.31	48.80
$R_f = 4.7 \text{ k}\Omega$	+162.17	0.10	0.24	24.41
$R_f = 10 \text{ k}\Omega$	+103.71	5.60×10^{-2}	0.18	15.63
AC inverter				
$R_f = 0$	0.061	224.03	0.149	148.75
$R_f = 4.7 \text{ k}\Omega$	0.038	112.02	0.068	74.55
$R_f = 10 \text{ k}\Omega$	0.022	71.63	0.056	47.70

TABLE II
EXPERIMENTAL SETUP RATINGS

Component	CHARACTERISTIC	MAGNITUDE
Power Transformer	U_{1n}	400 V
	I_{2n}	230.9 A (at 400 V)
	U_{2n}	50 – 150 – 230 – 400 V
	S_n	160 kVA
	Connection type	Yyn0
Power Converter	Power	140 kW
	$U_{DC \text{ max.}}$	900 V
	$I_{out \text{ max.}}$	200 A
	$f \text{ max.}$	25 kHz
	C	1638 μF
	$L_{filters}$	3 mH
Load	R_{phase}	50 Ω

(ac inverter side), the noise is much higher than in a case of a ground fault on the ac grid side.

Furthermore, the results for 0 Hz, 25 Hz, 50 Hz, and 5 kHz from simulations for ac grid side faults, negative pole faults, positive pole faults, and ac inverter side faults for ground fault resistances of 0, 4.7 k Ω , and 10 k Ω are displayed in Table I.

It can be seen that for ac grid side faults, the measured switching frequency is negligible compared with the obtained on the ac inverter side fault cases. Also, the first harmonic content ($f_1 = 50 \text{ Hz}$) is much lower in the ac inverter side. In case of not operating at 50 Hz but at 25 Hz, the latter component increases considerably. However, to achieve a good resolution in the FFT, enough recorded cycles are required. Therefore, more samples and calculation time are needed to analyze low frequency. The recording time should be studied according to the output frequency of the inverter (f_1'). Finally, for dc faults, the dc component is the most remarkable harmonic.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

To verify the operating principles and simulations, some experimental tests have been carried out on a 140-kW power converter.

The experimental setup consists of a 160-kVA main power transformer, which neutral has been connected to the ground with a high impedance grounding resistor. The transformer feeds an ac–dc power converter. Then, this power converter feeds a dc link where a 1638 μF capacitor is installed. Once the dc link is charged up to 650 V, a dc–ac inverter feeds a three-phase resistive load with variable frequency ($f_1' = 25 \text{ Hz}$). The experimental electrical scheme can be identified as Fig. 1, but replacing the motor with a 50 Ω three-phase resistor.

In case of fault, the grounding resistor will analyze the grounding voltage value and it can be known if a fault exists.

Table II sums up the main characteristics of the experimental setup and Figs. 18–21 show the elements of the experimental setup previously described.

Fig. 18. 160 kVA main power transformer of the experimental setup.

A grounding resistor of 4.7 k Ω has been placed between the neutral of the secondary winding of the power transformer and ground. A healthy test was carried out, i.e., with no ground faults in the electrical topology. In this case, if the terminal voltage is registered in R_g , a near to null value must be measured (see Fig. 22). The fluctuations are due to the return of leakage currents due to parasitic capacitances to the ground along the circuit.

The voltage fluctuations in case of a healthy state case have only high-frequency oscillations due to the system parasitic capacitances to ground. If an FFT is done to the healthy-state signal shown before in Fig. 22, the results displayed in Fig. 23 are obtained. They verify the healthy state conditions by only having high-frequency voltages.

Afterward, some faults were performed in different parts of the experimental setup. At a first stage, ground faults were performed on the ac grid side, i.e., between the main power transformer and the terminals of the power converter for ground fault resistance values of 0 Ω , 4.7 k Ω , and 10 k Ω .

The results obtained are shown in Fig. 24. The waveforms have a significant 50 Hz component and relatively low noise. The amplitude attenuation due to R_f corresponds to (1).

Fig. 19. 140 kW power converter.

Fig. 21. Oscilloscope measuring the grounding resistor terminal voltage during a faulty test.

Fig. 20. Three-phase resistive load [$Z = R = 50 \Omega$].

Fig. 22. Grounding resistor terminal voltage measured in a healthy-state test.

Second, if ground faults occur on the dc link, a waveform with a high presence of dc component shall be registered as the grounding resistor terminal voltage signal. In this case, the polarity of the waveform should be opposite to the faulty pole as said in Section III.

On the one hand, faults for the negative pole for fault resistances of 0Ω , $4.7 \text{ k}\Omega$, and $10 \text{ k}\Omega$ were performed and displayed in Figs. 25 –27, respectively. It can be seen the attenuation of the waveform amplitude, caused by R_f according to (1), the dc component staying positive in any case.

On the other hand, faults for the positive pole for fault resistances of 0Ω , $4.7 \text{ k}\Omega$, and $10 \text{ k}\Omega$ were also carried out and displayed in Figs. 28 –30, respectively. The results obtained were accordingly successful.

Finally, some faults were performed on the ac inverter side, where the 50Ω load was placed. In these cases, a deformed

Fig. 23. Grounding resistor terminal voltage FFT in a healthy-state test.

Fig. 24. Grounding resistor terminal voltage measured with ground faults on the ac grid side for $R_f = 0 \Omega$, $4.7 \text{ k}\Omega$, and $10 \text{ k}\Omega$.

Fig. 25. Grounding resistor terminal voltage measured with ground faults on the negative pole of the dc link for $R_f = 0 \Omega$.

waveform is obtained due to the 2 switching stages, one stage being the ac/dc rectifier and the other the dc/ac inverter. These both switching stages (in this case 12 IGBTs in total) make U_{gnd} be as shown in Figs. 31–33 for ground fault resistance of 0Ω , $4.7 \text{ k}\Omega$, and $10 \text{ k}\Omega$, respectively. The waveforms' asymmetries are provoked by the asynchronous switching between the rectifier and the inverter.

Once tested all the possibilities, an FFT was done for all the waveforms shown before (for a measurement time of 200 ms) obtaining the results shown in Table III for the following frequencies: 0 Hz, 25 Hz, 50 Hz, and 5 kHz.

The results clearly define where the fault is: if the ground fault is on the ac grid side, the fundamental harmonic of the grid (50 Hz) is the most remarkable and the switching frequency (5 kHz) is negligible. If the fault is on the dc side, the dc component is the most remarkable, and also a 5-kHz component appears. And

Fig. 26. Grounding resistor terminal voltage measured with ground faults on the negative pole of the dc link for $R_f = 4.7 \text{ k}\Omega$.

Fig. 27. Grounding resistor terminal voltage measured with ground faults on the negative pole of the dc link for $R_f = 10 \text{ k}\Omega$.

Fig. 28. Grounding resistor terminal voltage measured with ground faults on the positive pole of the dc link for $R_f = 0 \Omega$.

Fig. 29. Grounding resistor terminal voltage measured with ground faults on the positive pole of the dc link for $R_f = 4.7 \text{ k}\Omega$.

Fig. 30. Grounding resistor terminal voltage measured with ground faults on the positive pole of the dc link for $R_f = 10 \text{ k}\Omega$.

Fig. 31. Grounding resistor terminal voltage measured with ground faults on the ac inverter side of the power converter for $R_f = 0 \Omega$.

Fig. 32. Grounding resistor terminal voltage measured with ground faults on the ac inverter side of the power converter for $R_f = 4.7 \text{ k}\Omega$.

Fig. 33. Grounding resistor terminal voltage measured with ground faults on the ac inverter side of the power converter for $R_f = 10 \text{ k}\Omega$.

TABLE III
GROUNDING RESISTOR VOLTAGE, FFT OBTAINED IN EXPERIMENTS

Fault location Fault resistance (R_f)	$U_{\text{gnd.DC}}$ [V]	$U_{\text{gnd.25Hz}}$ [V]	$U_{\text{gnd.50Hz}}$ [V]	$U_{\text{gnd.5kHz}}$ [V]
AC Grid				
$R_f = 0$	0.084	0.410	241.04	2.108
$R_f = 4.7 \text{ k}\Omega$	0.170	0.424	120.41	2.924
$R_f = 10 \text{ k}\Omega$	0.098	0.259	77.43	3.996
Negative pole				
$R_f = 0$	+327.1	0.320	2.710	159.46
$R_f = 4.7 \text{ k}\Omega$	+163.4	0.191	1.024	79.93
$R_f = 10 \text{ k}\Omega$	+105.1	0.010	0.853	52.12
Positive pole				
$R_f = 0$	-331.2	0.516	2.647	158.93
$R_f = 4.7 \text{ k}\Omega$	-165.4	0.341	1.189	80.08
$R_f = 10 \text{ k}\Omega$	-106.2	0.045	0.828	52.19
AC inverter				
$R_f = 0$	-7.968	72.22	0.873	240.37
$R_f = 4.7 \text{ k}\Omega$	-5.613	35.20	0.911	125.59
$R_f = 10 \text{ k}\Omega$	-5.352	23.28	0.396	81.83

Fig. 34. Grounding resistor terminal voltage FFT for an ac grid side ground fault, dc negative pole ground fault, and an ac controlled side ground fault ($R_f = 0 \Omega$).

finally, if the ground fault is on the inverter side, the waveform FFT shows that the 25 Hz harmonic is higher than the 50 Hz harmonic and also 5 kHz switching harmonic appears.

Also, a representation of these FFT for different faults for a fault resistance of 0Ω is shown in Fig. 34.

On the whole, these results show a clear conformity among the theoretical principles and the results shown both through simulations and experimental tests. Thus, the accuracy of the ground fault detection method has been verified.

VI. CONCLUSION

A novel ground fault detection method for variable speed drives has been presented in this article.

The proposed method requires only the installation of a grounding resistor between the neutral of the power transformer and ground and it is suitable for any converter topology.

In case of a ground fault, a leakage current flows through the grounding resistor. The leakage current increases as the ground fault resistance decreases. Therefore, if the current or terminal voltage at the grounding resistor exceeds a certain threshold, the existence of a ground fault can be determined.

Moreover, thanks to the harmonic analysis of the aforementioned current or voltage waveform, the location where the ground fault has taken place can be determined as follows:

A. AC Grid Side

In case of ground fault on the ac grid side, the main harmonic corresponds to the power system frequency (50 or 60 Hz).

B. DC Bus

If the ground fault takes place on the dc bus of the converter, the waveform has a main dc component. Furthermore, by polarity analysis of the dc component, faults at the positive or negative terminals of the dc bus can be distinguished.

C. AC Inverter Side (Variable Frequency Side)

And finally, if the ground fault is located on the variable frequency ac side, the main component of the waveform corresponds to the operation frequency of the inverter. In the scenario in which the ac grid side and ac inverter side (variable speed drive side) operate at the same frequency, switching frequencies of the converter must be analyzed. If these frequencies show up in the waveform, then the fault is located on the ac inverter side.

The proposed technique has been validated by computer simulations and experimental tests in a typical variable speed drive comprising two IGBTs power converters.

These promising results show that the ground faults can be easily detected, and then, located. However, in the case of several converters fed from a unique power transformer the identification of the faulty converter is not evident. This could be the object of study future research works.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors would like to thank Mr. Lafoz from CIEMAT for his disposition and compromise with the research.

REFERENCES

- [1] J. M. Guerrero, G. Navarro, and C. A. Platero, "A novel ground faults detection method for variable speed drives," in *Proc. IEEE Int. Conf. Environ. Elect. Eng. 2020 IEEE Ind. Commercial Power Syst. Eur.*, 2020, pp. 1–6.
- [2] L. Qu and B. Zhang, "Research of PWM converter control method in electric vehicle," in *Proc. IEEE Veh. Power Propulsion Conf.*, 2008, pp. 1–5.
- [3] N. Weise and L. Doiron, "DQ current control of a bidirectional, isolated single-stage AC-DC converter," in *Proc. IEEE Appl. Power Electron. Conf. Expo.*, 2014, pp. 1888–1893.
- [4] Y. Inoue, S. Morimoto, and M. Sanada, "Comparative study of PMSM drive systems based on current control and direct torque control in flux-weakening control region," in *IEEE Trans. Ind. Appl.*, vol. 48, no. 6, pp. 2382–2389, Nov./Dec. 2012.
- [5] R. Granizo Arrabé, New methods and protection systems for AC and DC power networks. Doctoral Thesis, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, 2018.
- [6] Z. Wang, F. Zhuo, H. Yi, J. Wu, F. Wang, and Z. Zeng, "Analysis of dynamic frequency performance among voltage-controlled inverters considering virtual inertia interaction in microgrid," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Appl.*, vol. 55, no. 4, pp. 4135–4144, Jul./Aug. 2019.
- [7] V. Hertem, M. Ghandhari, J. B. Curis, O. Despouys, and A. Marzin, "Protection requirements for a multi-terminal meshed DC grid," in *Proc. Cigré Bologna Symp.*, 2011, pp. 13–15.
- [8] Y. Wang, J. Tian, Z. Chen, and X. Liu, "Model based insulation fault diagnosis for lithium-ion battery pack in electric vehicles," *Measurement*, vol. 131, pp. 443–451, 2019.
- [9] A. H. Bonnett and G. C. Soukup, "Cause and analysis of stator and rotor failures in three-phase squirrel-cage induction motors," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Appl.*, vol. 28, no. 4, pp. 921–937, Jul./Aug. 1992.
- [10] J. M. Guerrero, G. Navarro, C. A. Platero, P. Tian, and F. Blázquez, "A novel ground fault detection method for electric vehicle powertrains based on a grounding resistor voltage analysis," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Appl.*, vol. 56, no. 5, pp. 4934–4944, Sep./Oct. 2020.
- [11] J. Park, "Ground fault detection and location for ungrounded DC traction power systems," *IEEE Trans. Veh. Technol.*, vol. 64, no. 12, pp. 5667–5676, Dec. 2015.
- [12] S. Dhar, R. K. Patnaik, and P. K. Dash, "Fault detection and location of photovoltaic based DC microgrid using differential protection strategy," *IEEE Trans. Smart Grid*, vol. 9, no. 5, pp. 4303–4312, Sep. 2018.
- [13] C. Li, A. M. Gole, and C. Zhao, "A fast DC fault detection method using DC reactor voltages in HVdc grids," *IEEE Trans. Power Del.*, vol. 33, no. 5, pp. 2254–2264, Oct. 2018.
- [14] D. Paul, "Phasor diagram of a single-phase-ground fault current in a high-resistance grounded power system," in *Proc. IEEE/IAS 53rd Ind. Commercial Power Syst. Tech. Conf.*, 2017, pp. 1–6.
- [15] J. D. Gardell *et al.*, "Adjustable-speed drive motor protection applications and issues," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Appl.*, vol. 50, no. 2, pp. 1364–1372, Mar./Apr. 2014.
- [16] J. Hu, L. Wei, J. McGuire, and Z. Liu, "Ground fault location self-diagnosis in high resistance grounding drive systems," in *Proc. IEEE Energy Convers. Congr. Expo.*, 2014, pp. 3179–3185.
- [17] D. Paul, "Phase-Ground fault current analysis and protection of a high-resistance grounded power system," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Appl.*, vol. 56, no. 4, pp. 3306–3314, Jul./Aug. 2020.
- [18] T. Gruhn, J. Glenney, and M. Savostianik, "Type b ground-fault protection on adjustable frequency drives," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Appl.*, vol. 54, no. 1, pp. 934–939, Jan./Feb. 2018.
- [19] J. B. Roberts *et al.*, "Line differential protection system for a power transmission line," Korean Patent 10 084 047 8B1, Oct. 19, 2000.
- [20] F. Freschi, "High-frequency behavior of residual current devices," *IEEE Trans. Power Del.*, vol. 27, no. 3, pp. 1629–1635, Jul. 2012.
- [21] B. Bridger and T. A. Burse, "Operation of ground sensor relays under conditions of partial CT saturation," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Appl.*, vol. 33, no. 4, pp. 1111–1116, Jul./Aug. 1997.
- [22] M. A. Chowdhury, K. T. Reza, M. D. Alam, and E. Basher, "Third harmonic differential over current relay based protection system for stator ground fault in synchronous generator," in *Proc. 9th Int. Conf. Elect. Comput. Eng.*, 2016, pp. 606–609.
- [23] N. Safari-Shad and R. Franklin, "Adaptive 100% stator ground fault protection based on third-harmonic differential voltage scheme," *IEEE Trans. Power Del.*, vol. 31, no. 4, pp. 1429–1436, Aug. 2016.
- [24] C. A. Platero, M. Redondo, M. Pardo, and E. Rebollo, "Novel adaptive 100% stator ground fault protection based on the third harmonic measurement," *Proc. XXII Int. Conf. Elect. Machines*, 2016, pp. 2300–2305.
- [25] Y. Liang, K. Li, Z. Ma, and W. Lee, "Typical fault cause recognition of single-phase-to-ground fault for overhead lines in non-solidly earthed distribution networks," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Appl.*, vol. 56, no. 6, pp. 6298–6306, Nov./Dec. 2020.
- [26] M. Mitolo, R. Musca, and G. Zizzo, "A cost-effective solution for clearing high-impedance ground faults in overhead low-voltage lines," *IEEE Trans. Ind. Appl.*, vol. 55, no. 2, pp. 1208–1213, Mar./Apr. 2019.
- [27] M. M. Eissa, "Ground distance relay compensation based on fault resistance calculation," *IEEE Trans. Power Del.*, vol. 21, no. 4, pp. 1830–1835, Oct. 2006.
- [28] M. Saha, E. Rosolowski, and J. Izykowski, "Method and adaptive protection relay for power transmission lines," U.S. Patent 787 247 8B2. Jan. 11, 2011.
- [29] A. D. Filomena, R. H. Salim, M. Resener, and A. S. Bretas, "Ground distance relaying with fault-resistance compensation for unbalanced systems," *IEEE Trans. Power Del.*, vol. 23, no. 3, pp. 1319–1326, Jul. 2008.
- [30] Y. M. Yeap, N. Geddada, and A. Ukil, "Capacitive discharge based transient analysis with fault detection methodology in DC system," *Int. J. Elect. Power Energy Syst.*, vol. 97, 2018, pp. 127–137.
- [31] H. Funakoshi, "Charger, electric vehicle and method for detecting ground fault short-circuit in charging system," Japanese Patent 20 102 397 73A. Oct. 21, 2010.

- [32] C. A. P. Gaona, F. Blázquez, P. Frías, and M. Redondo, "A novel rotor ground-fault-detection technique for synchronous machines with static excitation," *IEEE Trans. Energy Convers.*, vol. 25, no. 4, pp. 965–973, Dec. 2010.
- [33] S. Turner, "Applying 100% stator ground fault protection by low frequency injection for generators," in *Proc. IEEE Power Energy Soc. Gen. Meet.*, 2009, pp. 1–6.
- [34] J. Sneath and A. D. Rajapakse, "Fault detection and interruption in an earthed HVDC grid using ROCOV and hybrid DC breakers," *IEEE Trans. Power Del.*, vol. 31, no. 3, pp. 973–981, Jun. 2016.

Accepted for publication